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Efficient Merging at Work Zones to Support Emergency Response in Mixed Traffic Environments: A Reward Weight Adjustment Method for Multi-Agent Reinforcement Learning

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ABSTRACT

Merging behaviours in work zones pose significant traffic management challenges due to lane closures that create bottlenecks and increase accident risk. In mixed traffic environments involving emergency vehicles (EVs), connected automated vehicles (CAVs), and human-driven vehicles, addressing these challenges becomes more complex. EVs, in particular, require priority movement to minimize response times, but their movement is often hindered by traditional traffic management strategies. While previous merging strategies have shown promising results in managing traffic flow, they fail to account for the unique challenges posed by different vehicle types in work zone environments. In this paper, we propose a new reward weight adjustment method for multi-agent proximal policy optimization based CAVs in work zone for emergency vehicles (MAPPO-WEV). The proposed method improves EV's response times without compromising travel time of other vehicles. MAPPO-WEV introduces a dynamic reward weighting mechanism that adjusts the importance weight of speed, headway, and merging behaviour based on the type and number of vehicles. This approach allows EVs to travel more freely while maintaining safety in mixed traffic conditions. The simulation results of MAPPO-WEV show significant improvements in both travel times and waiting times of EVs by 25% and 33% respectively compared to the Baseline method.

1 | Introduction

Work zones often disrupt traffic flow, particularly on two-lane highways where one lane is closed. This reduction in roadway capacity requires vehicles from both lanes to merge into a single open lane, often unexpectedly [1]. Evidence indicates that improper merging behaviours significantly contribute to work zone accidents, leading to severe traffic congestion and delays [2]. Making decisions in the merging area is especially difficult for vehicles, particularly in the complex environment where human-driven and machine-driven vehicles interact [3]. Recently, there

has been significant interest in utilizing (connected automated vehicles) CAVs for improving merging applications [4].

Advancements in CAV technologies have introduced robust communication systems, including vehicle-to-vehicle (V2V) and vehicle-to-infrastructure (V2I) protocols. These systems enable vehicles to share real-time data, facilitating cooperative decision-making during merging operations, known as cooperative merging [5]. While both on-ramp and work zone merging strategies share certain similarities, their control requirements differ in important ways. Some recent studies have focused on

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cooperative merging at highway on-ramps without relying on traffic signals [6, 7]. However, optimizing cooperative merging in work zones remains less explored, particularly in addressing the diverse objectives of different road users (e.g., emergency service vehicles), such as minimizing ambulance response times and enabling faster merging into the work zone. Among these users, emergency vehicles (EVs) play a critical role in mixed traffic environments.

EVs, such as fire trucks and ambulances, are essential to emergency medical services (EMS) systems, as they deliver essential equipment and personnel to accident sites. Reducing response times for these vehicles is highly important [8]. Response time, often defined as the duration from the moment an emergency call is received to the arrival of the EV, is a key performance metric [9, 10]. However, EVs frequently encounter delays caused by other vehicles obstructing their route, and the situation gets even worse with the unpredictable traffic flow, especially on busy highways. One example of such unpredictable conditions is work zones, where merging delays can make response times longer, highlighting the need for more efficient traffic management strategies with cooperative merging.

Three different methods have been proposed for cooperative merging, including rule-based, optimization-based, and learning-based methods [3]. Rule-based methods are based on a set of predefined rules and heuristics. Although they are simple and require minimal computational resources, they are not able to adapt and perform well in dynamic or unpredictable traffic situations [11]. Optimization-based methods use mathematical models to optimize traffic flow and reduce congestion. While effective, they often fail to handle the dynamic nature of mixed-traffic environments and struggle with real-time applications due to the need for precise computations [3].

To overcome the limitations of these methods, reinforcement learning (RL) has been introduced. RL integrated with deep neural networks can manage large state spaces, making it ideal for work zone control [11]. Vehicle agents can learn from numerous simulated scenarios, understanding the complex relationships between their actions and traffic operations, and ultimately finding strategies that maximize long-term rewards [11]. Despite its potential, current RL approaches still face important limitations when applied to cooperative merging in work zones. These approaches train vehicle agents in simplified, uniform traffic environments, without fully considering the complexities that arise from interactions between different types of vehicles. This presents a major limitation in real-world scenarios, where a mix of HDVs, CAVs, and EVs share the road. In practice, EVs encounter numerous operational challenges, particularly in scenarios where road capacity is reduced and merging behaviour is frequent. Although traffic laws require drivers to give way to EVs, noncompliance is common. This situation is worsened by the limitations of traditional EV alert systems, which are often difficult for drivers to perceive, especially in modern soundproof vehicles. Even when drivers do detect these signals, uncertainty about how to respond can lead to hesitation or unsafe manoeuvres. Although emergency vehicle approaching (EVA) systems can alert drivers that an EV is nearby, they typically lack clear guidance, which reduces their effectiveness in real-time traffic situations. These challenges highlight the urgent need for more advanced, context-

aware RL algorithms [12–14] that not only recognize the presence of different vehicle types but also incorporate a redesigned reward structure that prioritizes EVs and select situation-specific actions.

In this paper, we propose a novel multi-agent proximal policy optimization method for merging EVs in work zone areas (MAPPO-WEV). We formulate merging at work zone areas as a multi-agent RL (MARL) problem in which both CAVs and EVs act as decentralized agents, capable of communicating and receiving information from nearby agents. We determine the most effective reward structure for EVs based on the traffic demand. We highlight that the importance of speed, headway, and merging reward signals is dependent on the penetration rates of different vehicle types.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows: A detailed literature review is provided in Section 2. Section 3 introduces the background of the study. Section 4 presents the formulation of the work zone merging as a MARL problem. In Section 5, we describe our proposed method MAPPO-WEV. Section 6 details the experimental setup. Section 7 covers the results and discussion, and Section 8 concludes the paper.

2 | Literature Review

This section presents a detailed literature review focusing on driver behaviour toward approaching EVs, existing merging control strategies, and the application of RL techniques in work zone areas.

2.1 | Driver Behaviour Toward Approaching EVs

Driving in emergency situations is a challenging task for EVs [15, 16]. They face significant risks and limitations because of the surrounding traffic. It is generally expected that other drivers will yield the right of way to EVs based on traffic laws [17]. However, this is not always the case, and such noncompliance can create serious challenges for EV operations. In addition to the risk of collisions with other road users, which can result in fatalities each year [18–20], delays caused by other vehicles can slow down EMS systems. This increases the time to provide patients with the care they need [21, 22]. EVs use lights and sirens (L&S) to warn drivers that they are approaching; however, this method has certain drawbacks. Sirens can be hard to tell where they are coming from, and people often think they are farther away than they really are [20, 23]. Also, modern cars are well soundproofed, which can make it harder for drivers to hear sirens right away [24]. This delay can leave drivers with less time to react and move over safely. Additionally, since road users rarely encounter ambulances using L&S, they may have difficulty selecting the appropriate action to yield the right of way [25]. A suggested approach to help drivers interact more safely with emergency vehicle operators (EVOs) in traffic is to alert them through an EVA system [26]. An EVA warning notifies drivers with an early in-car warning that an EV is approaching and asks them to move out of the EV's way [27]. However, the effectiveness of these systems can be compromised by false alarms, which may lead to decreased compliance over time [24]. One key limitation of current EVA systems is that they only provide alerts without offering guidance on the specific

actions drivers should take. While drivers are notified that an EV is approaching, they are left to interpret and decide how to respond. This can lead to hesitation, confusion, or unsafe manoeuvres. One contributing factor to select an appropriate action is that drivers in developing countries often have less knowledge of traffic rules and are less likely to comply with them [28, 29]. As a result, EV drivers may struggle to anticipate the safest route, which may even increase the potential of a collision and delays [18]. A study reported that nearly half of the drivers in developing countries failed to take proper action when EMS ambulances approached. Although many respondents showed a generally positive attitude toward EVs, a considerable number still engaged in unsafe driving behaviour [30]. The National Safety Council and the Emergency Responder Safety Institute reported that most drivers tend to slow down near emergency scenes, which can lead to traffic delays and increase the risk of accidents. Additionally, some of the drivers admitted to nearly or actually hitting emergency personnel or vehicles, while many engage in distractions like filming, texting, or posting online as they were passing [31].

All of these limitations highlight the need for a more intelligent and adaptive approach, one that assists drivers in making appropriate, context-aware driving decisions such as accelerating and merging into the other lane, based on real-time traffic conditions and the types of surrounding vehicles.

2.2 | Merging Control Approaches for Work Zone Areas

To address the challenges of the merging control problems, previous studies have proposed several methods. The first category of merging control methods is the rule-based approach, which operates using predefined heuristic rules. Early merge (EM) and late merge (LM) are the most common rule-based strategies used to manage traffic flow and reduce congestion in work zones. EM encourages drivers to merge early, before reaching the work zone taper [32]. In contrast, LM encourages drivers in both the open and closed lanes to remain in their lanes until the merge point [33]. To the best of our knowledge, the only study that attempts to optimize vehicle behaviour to enhance the efficiency of EVs in work zones is [34]. This study introduces the ADAPT-EMERG algorithm, a rule-based approach designed to enhance decision-making and vehicle coordination for smoother merging. However, a limitation of rule-based methods is that they rely heavily on predefined rules and thresholds. Hence, they are less effective in adapting to the unexpected or dynamic nature of traffic environments [11].

Optimization-based methods employ mathematical modelling and computational algorithms to dynamically manage merging behaviours. In [35], a cooperative merging strategy using model predictive control (MPC) was introduced. In this cooperative merging, both merging and mainline vehicles adjust their trajectories in real-time to facilitate smooth merging. The MPC framework predicts future vehicle states and solves an optimization problem at each time step to minimize a cost function that includes safety, efficiency, and comfort considerations. In [36], a merging control strategy was proposed for work zones that combines traffic state prediction with a proportional-integral-

derivative (PID) controller. This approach dynamically adjusts merging instructions based on real-time traffic conditions to alleviate congestion and improve flow efficiency in mixed traffic environments. In another research, an advanced dynamic merging strategy, known as a lane-based dynamic control model, was presented [37]. However, the major drawback of optimization-based strategies, including MPC, is that they depend heavily on accurate traffic models, predictions, and control thresholds optimized by considering the relationships between different selected control variables. If the models do not align well with actual traffic behaviour, their effectiveness can decline [37, 38].

The third category comprises learning-based methods, particularly RL approaches. RL has been widely applied across intelligent transportation challenges, including mixed-traffic coordination [39–41], autonomous driving, and roadside decision-making [42–44], and even emerging applications that integrate large language models such as ChatGPT into traffic control frameworks [45]. Recent advances further demonstrate its scalability in realistic and large-scale settings, such as freeway corridors with multiple bottlenecks [46], multi-intersection urban networks [47, 48], and heterogeneous environments subject to disturbances and uncertainties [39–41]. Together, these studies underline the versatility of RL in improving congestion management, safety, and efficiency in complex traffic systems. While these approaches demonstrate the wide applicability of RL in intelligent transportation systems, they have not yet addressed the urgent and safety-critical merging needs of EVs in work zones, which is the focus of our study. Most previous RL research has mainly concentrated on the merging problem in on-ramp scenarios [49–51]. On-ramp merging and work zone merging differ in several key aspects that lead to fundamentally different control objectives and strategies. On-ramps usually involve vehicles entering at higher speeds, with long acceleration lanes and wider merging areas that give drivers room to adjust speed and accept gaps in mainline traffic. The goal in this setting is to keep the mainline flow as smooth as possible [11]. Work zone merging, by contrast, occurs under much more constrained conditions. Vehicles from a closed lane must move into an open lane, often without acceleration zones and within narrower lanes due to temporary traffic control devices. In these cases, cooperation between both lanes becomes essential for maintaining smooth traffic flow [52]. Another key difference is the role of speed management. Work zones impose reduced speed limits to improve worker safety, but driver non-compliance is common, creating significant speed variations that directly affect merging behaviour [53–55]. Furthermore, temporary traffic control devices, warning signs, and roadside construction activities alter the driving environment compared to highway ramps, further shaping driver behaviour during merging [56–58]. Because of these factors, smooth merging in work zones depends less on individual vehicles finding gaps and more on collective cooperation, with both lanes maintaining compatible speeds and flow rates. This makes cooperative merging strategies particularly critical in work zone environments [11]. Only a limited number of studies have applied RL to manage merging in work zone environments. In [11], a new merge control strategy was introduced for highway work zones, using an off-policy soft actor-critic (SAC) RL approach. The method is designed for a fully CAV environment, where metering zones are implemented in the open lane to help vehicles merge more safely and smoothly from the closed lane. Another research proposed

a joint trajectory optimization framework for CAVs operating in highway work zones. By applying a MARL approach, the study effectively coordinates lane changes, merging behaviour, and car-following actions to improve overall traffic flow and safety in work zone environment. Another research proposed a joint trajectory optimization framework for CAVs operating in highway work zones. By applying a MARL approach, the study effectively coordinates lane changes, merging behaviour, and car-following actions to improve overall traffic flow and safety in work zone environment [59].

All of the aforementioned studies assume a fully CAV environment, which does not accurately reflect real-world traffic conditions. In reality, traffic is highly dynamic, consisting of a mix of vehicle types with varying behaviours and priorities. Notably, the interaction between CAVs and HDVs is often overlooked. The effectiveness of any proposed control strategy can be significantly influenced by the penetration of different vehicle types. Therefore, it is crucial to consider scenarios where different types of vehicles interact, and the control system accounts for the varying importance and task priorities of each vehicle type.

Another key challenge in RL-based driving strategies lies in the structure of the reward function [60, 61]. A critical aspect is understanding how multiple driving objectives are mathematically integrated to form a single reward function, how various aspects of driving behaviour are combined within the reward function, and how the inability of this structure to adapt across varying driving conditions limits the model's capacity to generalize effectively. Most of the reviewed studies adopt a simple approach, adding together separate reward components to calculate the overall reward, as shown in Equation (1) [62–64]. However, this naive method lacks a mechanism for prioritizing or differentiating among the various goals and is insufficient when those objectives conflict with one another [65, 66]. For instance, assigning equal weight to safety and progress fails to reflect the critical importance of safety in real-world driving scenarios [67].

$$r = r_{\text{safety}} + r_{\text{progress}} + r_{\text{comfort}} + r_{\text{rules}} \quad (1)$$

Some studies have proposed methods in which the RL agent adjusts its behaviour based on specific features of the environment by switching between different reward setups [68–70]. This technique works well in simple situations, but it becomes difficult to use in more realistic scenarios due to the increasing complexity of real-world conditions. For example, in a highway section that includes a ramp, an autonomous vehicle might switch to a safety reward to ensure smooth merging and avoid collisions. However, during high traffic flow, this reward focus may cause the vehicle to behave too conservatively, slowing down excessively or hesitating to merge. Another drawback is that designing such systems often depends heavily on expert input. To enhance decision-making in autonomous driving using RL, recent advancements have explored more refined techniques that assign different levels of importance to each component of the reward function through the use of weighted values. In this setup, each attribute is given a specific weight to influence the overall learning outcome, as shown in Equation (2). In several studies, these weights have been manually fine-tuned to achieve desired behaviour [71–73]. However, this manual tuning process can be quite time consuming, often depends heavily on domain

expertise, and tends to lack adaptability across diverse driving conditions or environments.

$$r = w_{\text{safety}} \cdot r_{\text{safety}} + w_{\text{progress}} \cdot r_{\text{progress}} + w_{\text{comfort}} \cdot r_{\text{comfort}} + w_{\text{rules}} \cdot r_{\text{rules}} \quad (2)$$

These challenges highlight the need for more flexible and scalable solutions that can adaptively manage trade-offs between competing objectives in dynamic traffic environments. In contrast to conventional methods that rely on fixed reward weightings, our approach introduces a dynamic mechanism where the relative importance of reward components adjusts in response to traffic demand and the varying penetration rates of vehicle types with a particular focus on EVs response times.

3 | Background

This section provides the required background knowledge about RL and MARL.

In a RL framework, at each time step t , the agent interacts with its environment and based on the state $s_t \in S \subseteq \mathbb{R}^n$, takes an action $a_t \in A \subseteq \mathbb{R}^m$, and then receives a corresponding reward $r_t \in \mathbb{R}$ along with an updated state s_{t+1} at the next time step $t + 1$. The primary aim of the agent is to discover an optimal policy $\pi^* : S \rightarrow A$ that enables the selection of actions which result in the highest possible accumulated reward over time. The return at time step t , representing the total expected future reward, is computed as:

$$R_t = \sum_{k=0}^T \gamma^k r_{t+k}$$

In this expression, r_{t+k} denotes the reward obtained at each subsequent time step, and $\gamma \in (0, 1]$ is a discount coefficient that reduces the influence of rewards received further in the future. The Q -function (the state-action value function) for policy π , denoted as $Q^\pi(s_t, a_t)$, quantifies the expected total reward an agent can obtain by taking action a_t , in state s_t , and then following a given policy π . The optimal Q -function is described by the Bellman equation [74]:

$$Q^*(s_t, a_t) = \mathbb{E} \left[r(s_t, a_t) + \gamma \sum_{s_{t+1}} P(s_{t+1} | s_t, a_t) \cdot \max_{a_{t+1}} Q^*(s_{t+1}, a_{t+1}) \right] \quad (3)$$

where the next state s_{t+1} is drawn from the environment's transition dynamics $P(s_{t+1} | s_t, a_t)$.

3.1 | Multi-Agent Reinforcement Learning (MARL)

Multi-agent reinforcement learning (MARL) is a type of learning where multiple agents (such as robots or vehicles) learn to make decisions in an environment. Each agent is trying to achieve its own goals, but they may need to cooperate, compete, or both (mixed) with other agents to reach those goals [75]. In MARL, each agent learns through trial and error, just like in regular

RL, where they receive feedback (rewards or penalties) based on their actions. However, since there are multiple agents involved, they must consider not only the environment but also how other agents' actions affect their outcomes. This creates more complexity compared to single-agent RL. In MARL, parameter sharing enables multiple agents with similar roles to learn using the same set of neural network parameters. This approach simplifies the training process, as there is no need to build and maintain a separate model for each agent. It also makes the system more adaptable to changes in the number of agents, as agents can be added or removed without the need to retrain individual models, making the system more scalable and efficient [76]. Recent research has extended single-agent RL algorithms, such as proximal policy optimization (PPO), to MARL with parameter sharing, leading to the development of the MAPPO algorithm [77].

4 | Problem Definition: Work Zone Merging as MARL

In this section, the merging control problem in work zone areas is formulated as a partially observable Markov decision process (POMDP) [78], reflecting the reality that each vehicle can only detect and interact with nearby vehicles. In this research, since each agent can communicate only with a few neighboring vehicles and lacks information about those farther away, the problem is considered partially observable, requiring the agent to make decisions based on limited local observations. In our simulation setup, these observations (e.g., position, speed, headway of neighbouring vehicles) are obtained directly from the simulation of urban mobility (SUMO) environment through the TraCI interface. This corresponds to an idealized assumption of perfect V2X communication, where state information is transmitted without delay.

In this paper, we represent the work zone merging scenario in a mixed traffic environment. At each time step t each agent i observes its state s_i , interacts with its neighbouring agents $\mathcal{N}_i := \{j \mid \varepsilon_{ij} \in \varepsilon\}$ via the edge connections ε_{ij} , where $i \neq j$ and chooses an action a_i . The system's dynamics are described by the state transition distribution $P : S \times A \times S \rightarrow [0, 1]$. We adopt a decentralized MARL approach, where each agent $i \in \nu$, including connected and automated vehicles CAV_i and emergency vehicles EV_i , only has access to a partial view of the environment. The system is thus represented by the tuple $(a_i, s_i, r_i$ for $i \subseteq \nu, T$):

Action space: The action space A includes turning left, turning right, cruising, accelerating, and decelerating at high-level control [79]. Once action $a_i \in A$ is selected by agent i , lower-level controllers generate the necessary steering and throttle commands to guide CAVs and EVs accordingly.

State representation: The state of agent i , s_i , is a matrix of size $NN_i \times W$. NN_i (number of neighbourhood vehicles) is the number of vehicles observed by the agent vehicle, and W is referred to the number of features (presence of a vehicle nearby, longitudinal position x_1 , lateral position y , longitudinal speed v_x , and lateral speed v_y relative to the agent vehicle). We assume that each agent observes the closest NN_i vehicles within a 150-m range, where $NN_i = 5$, as this setting demonstrated the best

performance in previous research [76]. The overall system state is represented as the Cartesian product of the individual states of all agents, expressed as: $S = s_1 \times s_2 \times \dots \times s_N$.

Reward function: The reward function for each agent i at time step t is designed as a weighted sum of several components:

$$r_{i,t} = w_c r_c + w_s r_s + w_h r_h + w_m r_m \quad (4)$$

where w_c, w_s, w_h, w_m are positive weights for collision penalty, speed reward, headway time, and merging cost, respectively. The individual components are defined as follows:

Collision reward signal: r_c is -1 for each collision and 0 if no collision happens.

Speed reward signal: r_s is determined by the vehicle's speed relative to the desired speed range, ensuring it stays within safe limits. The formula is defined as:

$$r_s = \min \left(\frac{v_t - v_{\min}}{v_{\max} - v_{\min}}, 1 \right) \quad (5)$$

where v_t is the current speed of the agent vehicle, v_{\min} is the minimum speed (10 m/s), and v_{\max} is the maximum speed (30 m/s) [80, 81]. This ensures the vehicle receives a reward proportional to how close its speed is to the optimal range. It should be noted that for HDVs these values represent speed limits to ensure efficient and safe driving. For EVs and CAVs, however, v_{\min} and v_{\max} are only used as normalization parameters for reward shaping and do not act as hard constraints. Their actual speeds are determined dynamically by traffic conditions and vehicle interactions in the environment.

Headway reward signal: r_h penalizes when the time headway is below a threshold and rewards when it's above. It is calculated as:

$$r_h = \log \left(\frac{d_{\text{headway}}}{t_h \cdot v_t} \right) \quad (6)$$

where d_{headway} is the distance between the agent vehicle and its leader, t_h is a predefined threshold time headway (set to 1.2 s based on [82]), and v_t is the agent vehicle's speed.

Merging reward signal: r_m penalizes vehicles for spending excessive time in the merge lane, thus avoiding congestion. It is calculated as:

$$r_m = -\exp \left(-\frac{(x-L)^2}{10L} \right) \quad (7)$$

where x is the distance travelled by the agent on the merging zone, and L is the length of the merging zone. The penalty increases as the vehicle gets closer to the merge end, encouraging quicker merges to avoid delays.

5 | MAPPO-WEV

In this section, we introduce MAPPO-WEV, a multi-agent proximal policy optimization framework specifically designed

to facilitate efficient and safe merging of EVs in work zone environments. The proposed method addresses the limitations of existing MARL algorithms, which often overlook the varying importance of objectives across different vehicle types. MAPPO-WEV aims to achieve key objectives, mainly, prioritizing EVs to reduce their response times. To accomplish this, we present a novel adaptive reward mechanism that dynamically adjusts the weighting of reward components based on both vehicle type and real-time traffic demand. This section details the design rationale and implementation of the dynamic reward weighting method within the MAPPO-WEV framework.

5.1 | Dynamic Reward Weight Design

According to a state-of-the-art approach [76], the reward coefficients for different components, including collision, speed, headway, and merging are set as follows for CAVs:

$$\{w_c^{(CAV)}, w_s^{(CAV)}, w_h^{(CAV)}, w_m^{(CAV)}\} = \{200, 1, 4, 4\}$$

The high value assigned to the collision term has been shown to effectively discourage unsafe behaviour while maintaining a practical balance between speed and safety. As demonstrated in [76], setting w_c above 100 effectively eliminates collisions, while excessively large values overly penalize speed and lead to conservative driving. Their experiments show that $w_c = 200$ provides a reasonable trade-off between safety and traffic efficiency formulas.

To investigate the impact of reward weighting on EVs to prioritize them during the merging process, MAPPO-WEV introduces adaptive reward weights to better reflect EVs' urgency and priority in mixed traffic environment. The proposed reward weighting for EVs is as follows:

$$w_c^{EV} = w_c^{CAV} \quad (8)$$

$$w_s^{(EV)} = \max \left(0.5 \cdot w_s^{(CAV)}, \frac{N_{EV}}{N_{total}} \cdot w_s^{(CAV)} \right) \quad (9)$$

$$w_h^{(EV)} = \begin{cases} w_h^{(CAV)} \cdot \frac{2 \cdot N_{EV}}{N_{CAV}}, & \text{if } N_{CAV} > 0 \\ \frac{N_{EV}}{N_{total}} \cdot w_h^{(CAV)}, & \text{if } N_{CAV} = 0 \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

$$w_m^{(EV)} = \begin{cases} \frac{w_m^{(CAV)}}{2} \cdot \frac{N_{EV}}{N_{CAV}}, & \text{if } N_{CAV} > 0 \\ w_m^{(CAV)}, & \text{if } N_{CAV} = 0 \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

where $w_c^{(EV)}$, $w_s^{(EV)}$, $w_h^{(EV)}$, and $w_m^{(EV)}$ are collision reward, speed reward, headway reward, and merging reward weights for EVs, respectively. N_{EV} is the number of EVs in the environment. N_{CAV} is the number of CAVs in the environment. N_{total} is the total number of vehicles including CAVs, EVs, and HDVs in the environment.

This formulation increases the emphasis on keeping a balance between maintaining sufficient headway and minimizing merging time for EVs, based on the penetration rate of both CAVs and EVs. This scaling ensures that as more EVs are present, the reward function is dynamically updated to improve their

response times. Since the speed reward encourages vehicles to maintain a predefined speed range, its relative weight is adjusted for EVs based on their penetration level. When EVs are few in the network, their urgency requires flexibility to accelerate or manoeuvre beyond typical speed norms without being overly penalized, ensuring quicker response times. However, as the proportion of EVs in the traffic stream exceeds half and they become the dominant part of traffic flow, maintaining consistent speeds becomes increasingly important for overall traffic coordination. Therefore, the weight of this reward component should be increased accordingly to reflect this shift in traffic demand. As the number of EVs increases, maintaining safe headway becomes increasingly important. When more EVs are travelling freely and quickly through the environment, the risk of unsafe following distances rises which sometimes is at the cost of efficiency. Thus, the headway reward must carry more importance to ensure safety is not compromised. When no CAVs are present ($N_{CAV} = 0$), we use the EV share instead and set $w_h^{(EV)} = \frac{N_{EV}}{N_{total}} \cdot w_h^{(CAV)}$, which avoids division by zero and keeps the weight well-defined. Finally, when the number of EVs increases, the merging reward becomes relatively less important. In high-EV scenarios, EVs often need to merge in parallel and may compete for limited space. Since the environment becomes more saturated and coordinated merging becomes harder to achieve, overly emphasizing merging performance can lead to inefficient or conflicting behaviours. Therefore, the merging reward weight is reduced to allow agents to prioritize headway over aggressive merging, which is no longer as feasible in dense EV traffic.

5.2 | MAPPO-WEV Design Architecture

Figure 1 illustrates the architecture of the MAPPO-WEV framework integrated with the SUMO traffic simulator. The process begins by defining a traffic scenario, which includes EVs, CAVs, HDVs. Reward weights for EVs are dynamically determined based on the number of EVs and CAVs, whereas CAVs use predefined reward weights. These weights are applied to calculate reward components associated with collisions, speed, headway, and merging behaviour within a work zone. Each reward signal uses corresponding input features from the SUMO simulation environment. The total reward is computed as the weighted sum of these individual reward signals. Once the total reward is obtained, agents are trained using a neural network based on the MAPPO algorithm. At each timestep, MAPPO selects an action for each agent, which is then sent to the simulator. Based on the selected actions for the agent at its current state, the simulation environment updates its states and inputs. This loop continues until the maximum timestep is reached, either when all vehicles have exited the network or a limit of 10,000 steps is met, after which the episode ends. The next episode then begins. This cycle repeats until the total number of episodes reaches 10,000.

Algorithm 1 represents the training process of MAPPO-WEV, a MARL framework designed for mixed traffic environments including of CAVs, EVs, and HDVs. Each CAV and EV is treated as an independent learning agent. Initially, the SUMO environment and the actor-critic networks of all agents are initialized along with a shared replay buffer \mathcal{D} (lines 4–5). At the start of every training episode, the environment is reset, and the initial state

FIGURE 1 | Flowchart of MAPPO-WEV method.

ALGORITHM 1 | Multi-agent proximal policy optimization method for merging EVs in work zone area (MAPPO-WEV).

Require: Set of agents $i = \{i_1, i_2, \dots, i_n\}$ \triangleright CAVs and EVs

Require: Environment parameters:

1: $N_{EV}, N_{CAV}, N_{total}, L, v_{min}, v_{max}, t_h$

Require: Learning parameters:

2: learning rate α and discount factor γ .

Require: Max steps T_{max} , max episodes EP_{max}

3: Initialize SUMO simulation environment

4: Initialize MAPPO with actor π_θ and critic Q_ϕ for each agent

5: Initialize shared replay buffer \mathcal{D}

6: **for** episode $ep = 1$ to EP_{max} **do**

7: Reset environment and get initial state s_0

8: **for** step $t = 1$ to T_{max} **do**

9: **for** each agent $i_i \in \nu$ **do**

10: Select action $a_{i,t} \sim \pi_\theta(s_i)$ \triangleright Using MAPPO policy

11: **end for**

12: Execute joint actions $\{A_{i,t}\}_{i=1}^n$ in SUMO

13: Observe next state S_{t+1} and update vehicle info

14: Extract state info: *ispresent* (presence of a vehicle nearby), x_i (longitudinal relative position), y (lateral relative position), v_x (longitudinal relative speed), v_y (lateral relative speed)

15: **if** i_i is CAV **then**

16: $w_c \leftarrow 200, w_s \leftarrow 1, w_h \leftarrow 4, w_m \leftarrow 4$

17: **else if** i_i is EV **then**

18: $w_c \leftarrow 200$

19: $w_s \leftarrow \max\left(\frac{N_{EV}}{N_{total}} \cdot w_s^{(CAV)}, 0.5 \cdot w_s^{(CAV)}\right)$

20: **if** $N_{CAV} > 0$ **then**

21: $w_h \leftarrow w_h^{(CAV)} \cdot \frac{2N_{EV}}{N_{CAV}}$

22: **else**

23: $w_h \leftarrow \frac{N_{EV}}{N_{total}} \cdot w_h^{(CAV)}$

24: **end if**

25: **if** $N_{CAV} > 0$ **then**

26: $w_m \leftarrow w_m^{(CAV)} \cdot \frac{N_{EV}}{2N_{CAV}}$

27: **else**

28: $w_m \leftarrow w_m^{(CAV)}$

29: **end if**

30: **end if**

31: Compute rewards:

32: $r_c \leftarrow -1$ if collision else 0

33: $r_s \leftarrow \min\left(\frac{v_i - v_{min}}{v_{max} - v_{min}}, 1\right)$

34: $r_h \leftarrow \log\left(\frac{d_i}{t_h \cdot v_i}\right)$

35: $r_m \leftarrow -\exp\left(-\frac{(x_i - L)^2}{10L}\right)$

(Continues)

36: Compute total reward:

37: $r_{i,t} \leftarrow w_c r_c + w_s r_s + w_h r_h + w_m r_m$

38: Store $(S_t, A_{i,t}, R_{i,t}, S_{t+1}, i)$ in shared buffer \mathcal{D}

39: Update all agents using sampled minibatches from buffers:

40: **for** each agent $i_i \in \nu$ **do**

41: Sample minibatch of transitions from \mathcal{D}

42: Update actor π_θ and critic Q_ϕ via gradient descent

43: **end for**

44: $S_t \leftarrow S_{t+1}$

45: **end for**

46: **end for**

47: **Return** Trained policy π_θ

s_0 is retrieved (line 7). During each time step within an episode (lines 8–41), all agents independently select actions $a_{i,t}$ using their current policy network π_θ (lines 9–11). These actions are then executed in the simulation (line 12), leading to a transition to a new state s_{t+1} and updated traffic information (line 13). For each agent, feature information such as speed v_i , position x_i , and headway d_i is extracted (line 14). Depending on the vehicle type, reward weights are determined: CAVs use fixed weights (line 16), while EVs compute dynamic weights based on the penetration rate of vehicle types (lines 17–30). The agent-specific reward is computed based on multiple components: collision penalty r_c , speed reward r_s , headway reward r_h , and merging behaviour reward r_m (lines 31–35). These are combined into a weighted total reward $r_{i,t}$ (line 37), and the corresponding transition is stored in the shared replay buffer \mathcal{D} (line 38). Once transitions are collected, all agents update their actor and critic networks using sampled minibatches from the shared buffer \mathcal{D} (lines 39–43). The environment continues to evolve until the maximum number of steps T_{max} is reached, and the process repeats over multiple episodes up to EP_{max} (lines 6–46). Finally, the trained policies π_θ are returned for all agents (line 47), optimized through joint interaction in a mixed traffic environment.

6 | Experimental Setup

To validate the effectiveness of our proposed model framework and the adaptive reward design, we conduct experiments in a simulated highway environment using SUMO. The evaluation focuses on vehicle interactions within a work zone setting under mixed traffic conditions, consisting of CAVs, EVs, HDVs. By varying the proportions of vehicle types, we aim to assess how the reward formulation adapts to different traffic demands and supports efficient and safe merging behaviours.

Network settings: The simulation environment is modelled as a 520 m, two-lane highway segment that includes a 100 m work zone section and a 100 m post work zone to observe downstream effects (see Figure 2). The simulation operates with a fine-grained step length of 0.1 s, enabling precise vehicle movement and interaction modelling. An episode concludes either when all vehicles have exited the network or when the simulation reaches

FIGURE 2 | An illustration of the highway setting.

the maximum duration of 10,000 steps. Each scenario runs over 10,000 independent episodes to ensure the statistical reliability of the results. Each agent can observe up to 5 nearest neighbouring vehicles within a 150 m covering distance.

Traffic scenarios: Three distinct traffic scenarios are designed to evaluate system performance under varying EV and CAV penetration rates, while maintaining a constant number of HDVs:

- **Scenario 1:** 2 EVs (20%), 4 CAVs (40%), and 4 HDVs (40%),
- **Scenario 2:** 4 EVs (40%), 2 CAVs (20%), and 4 HDVs (40%),
- **Scenario 3:** 6 EVs (60%), 0 CAVs (0%), and 4 HDVs (40%).

In all scenarios, the number of HDVs was fixed at four (40%). Because HDVs are not modelled as learning agents in our framework, they serve as a stable background flow against which the EV and CAV agents operate. Our primary focus is to examine how varying EV and CAV proportions influence the merging process. Keeping the HDV share constant avoids additional variability from non-agent vehicles, ensures fair comparisons across scenarios, and still reflects a realistic level of human-driven traffic in mixed environments. HDVs follow the intelligent driver model (IDM), representing typical human car-following behaviour. In contrast, EVs and CAVs operate under the proposed MARL framework, using the MAPPO-WEV algorithm to optimize their merging behaviour based on vehicle type and traffic demand. In line with SUMO's vehicle class definitions, EVs are modelled as `vClass = "emergency"` vehicles, which by default are granted higher priority rights in traffic interactions. This reflects their real-world operational privilege and ensures they are treated consistently as priority vehicles in our simulations. All vehicles share consistent physical parameters: length ≈ 5 m, maximum acceleration (acceleration capability) 2.6 m/s^2 , maximum deceleration (deceleration capability) 4.5 m/s^2 , emergency deceleration (the maximal physically possible deceleration) 9 m/s^2 , and departure speed set to 0 m/s . Work zone enforces a reduced speed limit of 20 m/s , consistent with the settings reported in [83]. This reduced limit applies only within the lane-closure area, not in the upstream or downstream sections. Meanwhile, the speed reward function is applied throughout the entire simulation network, including upstream and downstream regions. However, emergency vehicles (`vClass = "emergency"`) are allowed to disobey this limit to reflect their priority rights. For further details on default vehicle parameters and class-specific behaviours, readers may refer to the SUMO documentation [84].

Performance criteria: To assess the impact of MAPPO-WEV on EVs' behaviour and the performance of the whole system, we analyse multiple performance metrics. The reported results are from the final 1000 episodes of training. These metrics include:

Average travel time: The average time spent by all vehicles (CAVs, EVs, and HDVs) that have exited the simulation,

Average emergency stops of all vehicles: Sudden and hard brakes are made to avoid a collision or react to unexpected traffic situations. SUMO defines emergency stops when the vehicle stops with a deceleration below -4.5 m/s^2 default value.

Average emergency braking of all vehicles: When a vehicle applies a deceleration exceeding its normal capabilities, SUMO defines it as an emergency braking. The deceleration threshold is 4.5 m/s^2 based on SUMO default values.

Average speed of EVs: The average trip speed of all EVs,

Average trip duration of EVs: The average travel time for EVs that have exited the simulation.

Average waiting time of EVs: The average time that EVs spend with the speed of 0 m/s .

Average time loss of EVs: The average time that EVs spend below their desired speed (i.e., the speed of the vehicle under free flow condition),

Average total travel time of EVs: The average of the total travel time of EVs.

These metrics are selected to evaluate both the safety (emergency stops, braking) and efficiency (speed, time loss) of EVs and all vehicles in the mixed environment.

7 | Results and Discussion

To analyse the impact of dynamically adjusting the speed ($w_s^{(EV)}$), headway ($w_h^{(EV)}$), and merging reward weight ($w_m^{(EV)}$) for EVs, we evaluate the performance across different scenarios by varying the reward weights and report the results in this section. This helps identify which criteria are most influential for each reward signal. When EVs are present in the environment, it becomes

FIGURE 3 | Average EV waiting time vs. episodes under different speed reward weight settings (Scenario 1). Colour map and definitions: red: Baseline, $w_s^{(CAV)}$; green: CAV/EV ratio weighted, $\frac{N_{CAV}}{N_{EV}} w_s^{(CAV)} = 2 w_s^{(CAV)}$; blue: EV/CAV ratio weighted, half weight, and 1/EV ratio weighted, $\frac{N_{EV}}{N_{CAV}} w_s^{(CAV)} = 0.5 w_s^{(CAV)} = \frac{1}{N_{EV}} w_s^{(CAV)}$; purple: EV ratio weighted, $\frac{N_{EV}}{N_{total}} w_s^{(CAV)} = 0.2 w_s^{(CAV)}$.

critically important to adjust the emphasis on different reward components and dynamically adapt their weights within RL systems based on context. Changing these weights effectively alters the priority assigned to each decision of agents. This is essential because, during an EV's arrival, vehicles may need to compromise on certain objectives, such as safety margins or overall traffic efficiency, to reduce EVs' response time.

We have also reported the results under different vehicle densities, simultaneous weight adjustment of reward signals and the impact of delay and penetration rate.

7.1 | Selected Key Simulation Results Overview and Takeaways

This section highlights the most important outcomes presented in Tables 1–3 and Figures 3–5.

Scenario 1 (mixed fleet, few EVs): When EVs are few in the network, halving the EV speed weight ($w_s^{(EV)}=0.5 w_s^{(CAV)}$), while keeping the headway ($w_h^{(EV)}=1 w_h^{(CAV)}$) and merging ($w_m^{(EV)}=1 w_m^{(CAV)}$) weights unchanged, yields the best outcomes. This setting improves EV trip duration by **7.83%**, reduces EV waiting time by **22.63%**, and decreases EV time loss by **8.66%**, while lowering overall network travel time by **5.54%** compared with the Baseline.

Scenario 2 (higher EV penetration rate with CAV support): As the number of EVs increases and coordination with CAVs becomes available, maintaining safe headways becomes more critical. Therefore, higher headway and lower merging weights are assigned to EVs to balance efficiency and safety: $w_s^{(EV)}=0.5 w_s^{(CAV)}$, $w_h^{(EV)}=4 w_h^{(CAV)}$, and $w_m^{(EV)}=0.25 w_m^{(CAV)}$. This adaptive headway/merging emphasis produces the largest gains, reducing EV trip duration by **73.75%**, EV waiting time by **85.33%**, and EV time loss by **76.09%**, with EV speed increasing by up to **134.87%**.

FIGURE 4 | Average EV waiting time versus episodes under different headway reward weight settings (Scenario 1). Colour map and definitions: red: Baseline, $w_h^{(CAV)}$; green: CAV/EV ratio weighted, $\frac{N_{CAV}}{N_{EV}} w_h^{(CAV)} = 2 w_h^{(CAV)}$; purple: EV ratio weighted, $\frac{N_{EV}}{N_{total}} w_h^{(CAV)} = 0.2 w_h^{(CAV)}$; blue: EV/CAV ratio weighted and 1/EV ratio weighted, $\frac{N_{EV}}{N_{CAV}} w_h^{(CAV)} = \frac{1}{N_{EV}} w_h^{(CAV)} = 0.5 w_h^{(CAV)}$.

FIGURE 5 | Average EV waiting time versus episodes under different merging reward weight settings (Scenario 1). Colour map and definitions: red: Baseline, $w_m^{(CAV)}$; green: CAV/EV ratio weighted, $\frac{N_{CAV}}{N_{EV}} w_m^{(CAV)} = 2 w_m^{(CAV)}$; blue: EV/CAV ratio weighted, half weight, and 1/EV ratio weighted, $\frac{N_{EV}}{N_{CAV}} w_m^{(CAV)} = \frac{1}{N_{EV}} w_m^{(CAV)} = 0.5 w_m^{(CAV)}$.

Scenario 3 (no CAVs, EV-dominant): In a network dominated by EVs and without CAV coordination, Using moderate reward weights, $w_s^{(EV)}=0.6 w_s^{(CAV)}$, $w_h^{(EV)}=0.6 w_h^{(CAV)}$, and $w_m^{(EV)}=1 w_m^{(CAV)}$, achieves a balanced performance by ensuring sufficient headway while allowing smooth merging. This setting improves EV trip duration by **39.71%**, reduces waiting time by **50.66%**, and decreases time loss by **43.07%** compared with the Baseline.

The urgency of EVs requires flexibility to accelerate or manoeuvre beyond typical speed norms, so the speed reward weight is reduced when EVs are few. As EVs become dominant, this weight increases adaptively with their penetration rate to promote smoother coordination. For headway, when no CAVs are present, the weight scales with the EV penetration rate, while in mixed EV–CAV traffic, it becomes more important to prevent unsafe headways as EVs travel faster and more freely. Finally, as EV numbers grow, the merging reward becomes less critical since

TABLE 1 | Performance metrics comparison for the last 1000 episodes across three scenarios and different speed reward weights.

Scenario	Performance metric	Baseline	$w_s^{(EV)} =$				
			EV ratio weighted	CAV/EV ratio weighted	Half weight	EV/CAV ratio weighted	1/EV ratio weighted
Scenario 1	Average travel time of all vehicles	76.94	105.86 (+37.59%)	112.9 (+46.74%)	72.68 (-5.54%)	72.68 (-5.54%)	72.68 (-5.54%)
	Average emergency Stops	1.12	1.2 (+7.14%)	1.22 (+8.93%)	1.44 (+28.57%)	1.44 (+28.57%)	1.44 (+28.57%)
	Average emergency braking	2.08	1.38 (-33.65%)	2.24 (+7.69%)	2.44 (+17.31%)	2.44 (+17.31%)	2.44 (+17.31%)
	Average speed of EVs	5.94	5.27 (-11.28%)	6.74 (+13.47%)	8.65 (+45.62%)	8.65 (+45.62%)	8.65 (+45.62%)
	Average trip duration of EVs	100.15	152.3 (+52.07%)	158.45 (+58.21%)	92.31 (-7.83%)	92.31 (-7.83%)	92.31 (-7.83%)
	Average waiting time of EVs	5.48	18.21 (+232.30%)	15.86 (+189.42%)	4.24 (-22.63%)	4.24 (-22.63%)	4.24 (-22.63%)
Scenario 2	Average time loss of EVs	90.63	142.78 (+57.54%)	148.93 (+64.33%)	82.78 (-8.66%)	82.78 (-8.66%)	82.78 (-8.66%)
	Average total travel time of EVs	200.3	304.61 (+52.08%)	316.91 (+58.22%)	184.62 (-7.83%)	184.62 (-7.83%)	184.62 (-7.83%)
	Average travel time of all vehicles	233.63	252.49 (+8.07%)	111.79 (-52.15%)	111.79 (-52.15%)	146.86 (-37.14%)	249.26 (+6.69%)
	Average emergency stops	1.08	1.12 (+3.70%)	1.14 (+5.56%)	1.14 (+5.56%)	1.04 (-3.70%)	1.04 (-3.70%)
	Average emergency braking	1.92	2.16 (+12.50%)	2.22 (+15.63%)	2.22 (+15.63%)	1.82 (-5.21%)	0.92 (-52.08%)
	Average speed of EVs	3.47	5.0 (+44.09%)	5.96 (+71.76%)	5.96 (+71.76%)	5.07 (+46.11%)	3.36 (-3.17%)
Scenario 3	Average trip duration of EVs	310.91	354.74 (+14.10%)	144.16 (-53.63%)	144.16 (-53.63%)	193.65 (-37.72%)	367.31 (+18.14%)
	Average waiting time of EVs	53.31	63.24 (+18.63%)	16.58 (-68.90%)	16.58 (-68.90%)	25.27 (-52.60%)	78.62 (+47.48%)
	Average time loss of EVs	301.5	345.33 (+14.54%)	134.74 (-55.31%)	134.74 (-55.31%)	184.23 (-38.90%)	357.89 (+18.70%)
	Average total travel time of EVs	1243.64	1418.98 (+14.10%)	576.65 (-53.63%)	576.65 (-53.63%)	774.6 (-37.72%)	1469.24 (+18.14%)
	Average travel time of all vehicles	90.54	86.84 (-4.09%)	87.76 (-3.07%)	88.9 (-1.81%)	Not applicable	155.31 (+71.54%)
	Average emergency stops	1.32	0.94 (-28.79%)	1.6 (+21.21%)	0.92 (-30.30%)	Not applicable	0.98 (-25.76%)
Scenario 3	Average emergency braking	1.16	1.46 (+25.86%)	3.44 (+196.55%)	1.08 (-6.90%)	Not applicable	2.42 (+108.62%)
	Average speed of EVs	7.57	8.15 (+7.66%)	7.04 (-7.00%)	8.07 (+6.61%)	Not applicable	6.37 (-15.85%)
	Average trip duration of EVs	121.28	110.6 (-8.81%)	114.2 (-5.84%)	123.52 (+1.85%)	Not applicable	228.37 (+88.30%)
	Average waiting time of EVs	9.79	8.83 (-9.81%)	12.68 (+29.52%)	10.55 (+7.76%)	Not applicable	40.67 (+315.42%)
	Average time loss of EVs	111.83	101.15 (-9.55%)	104.74 (-6.34%)	114.06 (+1.99%)	Not applicable	218.92 (+95.76%)
	Average total travel time of EVs	727.73	663.66 (-8.80%)	685.2 (-5.84%)	741.13 (+1.84%)	Not applicable	1370.23 (+88.29%)

Note: "Not applicable" values occur when the number of CAVs is zero, causing a division by zero in reward weight calculations.

TABLE 2 | Performance metrics comparison for the last 1000 episodes across three scenarios using different roadway reward weights.

Scenario	Performance metric	Baseline	$w_h^{(EV)} =$				
			EV ratio weighted	EV/CAV ratio weighted	CAV/EV ratio weighted	2×EV/CAV ratio weighted	1/EV ratio weighted
Scenario 1	Average travel time	76.94	96.80 (+25.79%)	109.20 (+42.00%)	140.26 (+82.26%)	76.94 (+0.00%)	109.20 (+42.00%)
	Average emergency stops	1.12	1.18 (+5.36%)	1.34 (+19.64%)	1.00 (-10.71%)	1.12 (+0.00%)	1.34 (+19.64%)
	Average emergency braking	2.08	1.92 (-7.69%)	1.90 (-8.65%)	1.94 (-6.73%)	2.08 (+0.00%)	1.90 (-8.65%)
	Average speed of EVs	5.94	4.91 (-17.38%)	4.45 (-25.08%)	3.63 (-38.89%)	5.94 (+0.00%)	4.45 (-25.08%)
	Average trip duration of EVs	100.15	136.7 (+36.47%)	165.43 (+65.15%)	207.42 (+107.03%)	100.15 (+0.00%)	165.43 (+65.15%)
	Average waiting time of EVs	5.48	11.02 (+101.09%)	15.67 (+185.77%)	21.43 (+291.24%)	5.48 (+0.00%)	15.67 (+185.77%)
Scenario 2	Average time loss of EVs	90.63	127.18 (+40.29%)	155.91 (+71.98%)	197.91 (+118.43%)	90.63 (+0.00%)	155.91 (+71.98%)
	Average total travel time of EVs	200.31	273.4 (+36.47%)	330.85 (+65.15%)	414.84 (+107.03%)	200.31 (+0.00%)	330.85 (+65.15%)
	Average travel time	233.63	122.3 (-47.65%)	90.77 (-61.15%)	111.67 (-52.21%)	85.43 (-63.44%)	97.02 (-58.47%)
	Average emergency stops	1.08	1.24 (+14.81%)	1.18 (+9.26%)	1.14 (+5.56%)	1.2 (+11.11%)	1.14 (+5.56%)
	Average emergency braking	1.92	2.24 (+16.67%)	2.52 (+31.25%)	2.26 (+17.71%)	2.18 (+13.54%)	2.14 (+11.46%)
	Average speed of EVs	3.47	5.08 (+46.41%)	5.44 (+56.78%)	6.94 (+99.71%)	5.68 (+63.70%)	5.20 (+49.86%)
Scenario 3	Average trip duration of EVs	310.91	158.57 (-49.00%)	122.61 (-60.57%)	144.22 (-53.63%)	111.61 (-64.1%)	127.42 (-59.02%)
	Average waiting time of EVs	53.31	17.00 (-68.11%)	12.00 (-77.49%)	13.73 (-74.25%)	10.10 (-81.06%)	18.02 (-66.20%)
	Average time loss of EVs	301.50	149.16 (-50.52%)	103.20 (-65.75%)	134.80 (-55.31%)	102.19 (-66.10%)	118.00 (-60.86%)
	Average total travel time of EVs	1243.64	634.31 (-49.00%)	510.46 (-58.96%)	576.88 (-53.63%)	446.47 (-64.11%)	509.68 (-59.02%)
	Average travel time	90.54	73.27 (-19.06%)	Not applicable	146.52 (+61.86%)	Not applicable	85.87 (-5.16%)
	Average emergency stops	1.32	1.12 (-15.15%)	Not applicable	1.26 (-4.55%)	Not applicable	1.60 (+21.21%)
Scenario 3	Average emergency braking	1.16	1.80 (+55.17%)	Not applicable	1.20 (+3.45%)	Not applicable	2.48 (+113.79%)
	Average speed of EVs	7.57	8.46 (+11.76%)	Not applicable	6.71 (-11.36%)	Not applicable	7.85 (+3.70%)
	Average trip duration of EVs	121.28	95.71 (-21.11%)	Not applicable	198.51 (+63.69%)	Not applicable	113.29 (-6.59%)
	Average waiting time of EVs	9.79	6.00 (-38.75%)	Not applicable	27.19 (+177.72%)	Not applicable	9.74 (-0.51%)
	Average Time loss of EVs	111.83	86.26 (-22.88%)	Not applicable	189.05 (+69.00%)	Not applicable	103.84 (-7.14%)
	Average total travel time of EVs	727.73	574.29 (-21.11%)	Not applicable	1191.08 (+63.69%)	Not applicable	679.78 (-6.59%)

Note: "Not applicable" values occur when the number of CAVs is zero, causing a division by zero in reward weight calculations.

TABLE 3 | Performance metrics comparison for the last 1000 episodes across three scenarios using different merging reward weights.

Scenario	Performance Metric	Baseline	$w_m^{(EV)} =$			1/EV Ratio Weighted
			CAV/EV Ratio Weighted	EV/CAV Ratio Weighted	Half CAV/EV Ratio Weighted	
Scenario 1	Average travel time	76.94	108.79 (+41.39%)	87.12 (+13.23%)	76.94 (0.00%)	87.12 (+13.23%)
	Average emergency stops	1.12	1.34 (+19.64%)	0.86 (-23.21%)	1.12 (0.00%)	0.86 (-23.21%)
	Average emergency braking	2.08	2.10 (+0.96%)	1.72 (-17.31%)	2.08 (0.00%)	1.72 (-17.31%)
	Average speed of EVs	5.94	4.49 (-24.41%)	5.25 (-11.78%)	5.94 (0.00%)	5.25 (-11.78%)
	Average trip duration of EVs	100.15	160.79 (+60.50%)	113.35 (+13.13%)	100.15 (0.00%)	113.35 (+13.13%)
	Average waiting time of EVs	5.48	17.75 (+223.54%)	10.61 (+93.61%)	5.48 (0.00%)	10.61 (+93.61%)
Scenario 2	Average time loss of EVs	90.63	151.27 (+66.85%)	103.84 (+14.57%)	90.63 (0.00%)	103.84 (+14.57%)
	Average total travel time of EVs	200.30	321.58 (+60.47%)	226.71 (+13.18%)	200.30 (0.00%)	226.71 (+13.18%)
	Average travel time	233.63	115.58 (-50.52%)	304.88 (+30.48%)	75.95 (-67.49%)	115.58 (-50.52%)
	Average emergency stops	1.08	1.60 (+48.15%)	0.76 (-29.63%)	1.3 (+20.37%)	1.60 (+48.15%)
	Average emergency braking	1.92	2.68 (+39.58%)	2.86 (+48.95%)	2.86 (+48.96%)	2.86 (+49.95%)
	Average speed of EVs	3.47	4.42 (+27.38%)	3.52 (+1.44%)	6.82 (+96.54%)	4.42 (+27.38%)
Scenario 3	Average trip duration of EVs	310.91	151.59 (-51.25%)	409.67 (+31.75%)	101.64 (-67.31%)	151.59 (-51.25%)
	Average waiting time of EVs	53.31	17.43 (-67.31%)	75.63 (+41.81%)	8.58 (-83.91%)	17.43 (-67.31%)
	Average time loss of EVs	301.50	142.18 (-52.85%)	400.26 (+32.73%)	92.22 (-69.41%)	142.18 (-52.85%)
	Average total travel time of EVs	1243.64	606.37 (-51.25%)	1638.67 (+31.73%)	406.59 (-67.31%)	606.37 (-51.25%)
	Average travel time	90.54	111.69 (+23.39%)	Not applicable	111.69 (+23.39%)	134.41 (+48.45%)
	Average emergency stops	1.32	1.44 (+9.09%)	Not applicable	1.44 (+9.09%)	1.14 (-13.63%)
Scenario 3	Average emergency Braking	1.16	2.58 (+122.41%)	Not applicable	2.58 (+122.41%)	0.82 (-29.31%)
	Average speed of EVs	7.57	6.02 (-20.47%)	Not applicable	6.02 (-20.47%)	6.11 (-19.40%)
	Average trip duration of EVs	121.29	145.45 (+19.91%)	Not applicable	145.45 (+19.91%)	140.66 (+15.96%)
	Average waiting time of EVs	9.79	16.53 (+68.86%)	Not applicable	16.53 (+68.86%)	12.43 (+26.96%)
	Average time loss of EVs	111.83	135.99 (+21.58%)	Not applicable	135.99 (+21.58%)	131.21 (+17.30%)
	Average total travel time of EVs	727.73	872.67 (+19.90%)	Not applicable	872.67 (+19.90%)	843.96 (+15.96%)

Note: "Not applicable" values occur when the number of CAVs is zero, causing a division by zero in reward weight calculations.

frequent parallel merges in dense traffic can cause conflicts; thus, it is reduced to prioritize safe spacing over aggressive merging.

7.2 | Impact of Speed Reward Weight on Performance

The results in Table 1 demonstrate how adjusting the weight of the speed reward ($w_s^{(EV)}$) influences the performance of EVs in the work zone merging scenario. To understand the effects of speed reward weight we tested in six settings: the baseline ($w_s^{(EV)}$), EV ratio weighted ($\frac{N_{EV}}{N_{total}} \times w_s^{(CAV)}$), CAV/EV ratio weighted ($\frac{N_{CAV}}{N_{EV}} \times w_s^{(CAV)}$), half weight ($0.5 \times w_s^{(CAV)}$), EV/CAV ratio weighted ($\frac{N_{EV}}{N_{CAV}} \times w_s^{(CAV)}$), and 1/EV ratio weighted ($\frac{1}{N_{EV}} \times w_s^{(CAV)}$).

7.2.1 | Performance Under Scenario 1

7.2.1.1 | Speed Reward CAV/EV Ratio Weighted. Here, the traffic mix includes 2 EVs, 4 CAVs, and 4 HDVs, when the speed reward weight is increased ($\frac{N_{CAV}}{N_{EV}} \times w_s^{(CAV)} = 2 \times w_s^{(CAV)}$), EVs maintain consistent speeds between the defined range (10–30 m/s). This results in a higher average speed for EVs compared to the Baseline by 13.47%. Prioritising EVs over other vehicles increases the average travel time for all vehicles by 46.74%, the waiting time for EVs by 189.42%, and the total travel time for EVs by 58.22%.

In this scenario, both trip duration and waiting times of EVs increase. Although the average speed may appear higher, merging conflicts introduce additional delays that ultimately raise the overall travel time for EVs. This behaviour also compromises safety, as reflected by the increased average number of emergency stops and emergency braking by 8.93% and 7.69%, respectively.

7.2.1.2 | Speed Reward EV/CAV Ratio Weighted, Half Weight, and 1/EV Ratio Weighted. : Conversely, when the speed reward is reduced ($\frac{N_{EV}}{N_{CAV}} \times w_s^{(CAV)} = \frac{1}{N_{EV}} \times w_s^{(CAV)} = 0.5 \times w_s^{(CAV)}$), EVs are less penalized for fluctuated speeds, allowing them to behave more aggressively to minimize delay-related penalties. As a result, this setting achieves the highest average speed (8.65 m/s), and the shortest average travel time for all vehicles (72.68 s), with lower waiting time and time loss of EVs compared to the other scenarios. However, this gain in efficiency comes with a slight increase in higher emergency stops and braking events compared to the baseline by 28.57% and 17.31%, respectively, indicating more frequent abrupt manoeuvres in the traffic stream.

These findings reveal that the best setting for the speed reward weight of EVs ($w_s^{(EV)}$) for this scenario is ($0.5 \times w_s^{(CAV)}$), which can also be achieved by the proposed MAPPO-WEV method.

7.2.1.3 | Speed Reward EV Ratio Weighted. Another important observation is the performance under the weight setting $\frac{N_{EV}}{N_{total}} \times w_s^{(CAV)} = 0.2 \times w_s^{(CAV)}$. This reflects an adaptive weighting approach based on the proportion of EVs (MAPPO-WEV) in the environment. While this method promotes fairness

among vehicle types, it can underestimate the importance of EV objectives when there are only a few EVs present. As a result, EV performance may decline, as seen in the higher average travel time for all vehicles (105.86 s), average waiting time (18.21 s), and average time loss of EVs (142.78 s).

7.2.1.4 | Average EV Waiting Time Under Different Speed Reward Weights. Figure 3 shows the average EV waiting time across training episodes for six speed reward weight settings: baseline shown in red; CAV/EV ratio weighted shown in green; EV/CAV ratio weighted, half weight, and 1/EV ratio weighted shown in blue; and EV ratio weighted shown in purple. The findings are consistent with Table 1: the blue setting consistently attains the lowest waiting times, green remains highest, and red and purple lie between. Notably, in Scenario 1 the MAPPO-WEV rule selects $w_s^{(EV)} = \max(0.5, 0.2) w_s^{(CAV)} = 0.5 w_s^{(CAV)}$, which corresponds to the blue line and yields lower EV waiting time than the Baseline over the final evaluation window, supporting the adaptive weighting in Equation (9).

7.2.2 | Performance Under Scenario 2

7.2.2.1 | Speed Reward CAV/EV Ratio Weighted and Half Weight. In Scenario 2, where the traffic mix includes 4 EVs, 2 CAVs, and 4 HDVs, a similar trend as experienced in Scenario 1 can be observed. When the speed reward is decreased ($\frac{N_{CAV}}{N_{EV}} \times w_s^{(CAV)} = 0.5 \times w_s^{(CAV)}$), EVs tend to maintain a higher speed, where we see the average speed of EVs increases by 71.76%, while average trip duration of EVs (144.16 s), average waiting time (16.58 s), and average time loss (134.74 s) all decrease significantly compared to the Baseline (310.91 s, 53.31 s, and 301.50 s, respectively). However, this gain in efficiency comes with a slight increase in the average emergency stops (1.14) and average braking events (2.22), indicating more aggressive driving behaviour.

7.2.2.2 | Speed Reward EV/CAV Ratio Weighted. Conversely, under the weight setting $\frac{N_{EV}}{N_{CAV}} \times w_s^{(CAV)} = 2 \times w_s^{(CAV)}$, EV performance deteriorates compared to the best setting. The average speed of EVs drops to 5.07 m/s, while the trip duration of EVs (193.65 s) and total travel time of EVs (774.60 s) increase. Although emergency stops (1.04) and braking of EVs (1.82) slightly improve, this setting shows that overly conservative reward signals may lead to increased delays, despite marginal safety benefits.

7.2.2.3 | Speed Reward EV Ratio Weighted. In this setting ($\frac{N_{EV}}{N_{total}} \times w_s^{(CAV)} = 0.4 \times w_s^{(CAV)}$), the speed weight reward for EVs decreased. This implies that maintaining speed within the optimal range is given less importance for EVs. While their average speed improves to 5.0 m/s (+44.09%), key performance metrics worsen: average trip duration for EVs increases by 14.10%, average waiting time of EVs by 18.63%, and average time loss of EVs by 14.54%. These results suggest that this reward weight is too weak to drive efficient EV behaviour.

7.2.2.4 | Speed Reward 1/EV Ratio Weighted. With $N_{EV}=4$, this sets $w_s^{(EV)}$ to $0.25 w_s^{(CAV)}$. The weaker speed incentive leads to slightly lower EV speed (3.36 m/s, -3.17%) and notably worse efficiency: EV trip duration rises to 367.31 s (+18.14%),

waiting time to 78.62 s (+47.48%), time loss to 357.89 s (+18.70%), and total EV travel time to 1469.24 s (+18.14%).

7.2.3 | Performance Under Scenario 3

7.2.3.1 | Speed Reward Half Weight. In Scenario 3, which includes 6 EVs and 4 HDVs (no CAVs), setting $w_s^{(EV)} = 0.5 w_s^{(CAV)}$ yields an average EV speed of 8.07 m/s and lowers waiting time (10.55 s), time loss (114.06 s), and emergency braking events (1.08) relative to the baseline.

7.2.3.2 | Speed reward CAV/EV Ratio Weighted. In this scenario, there are no CAVs, which causes the weight formula $\frac{N_{CAV}}{N_{EV}} \times w_s^{(CAV)}$ to evaluate to zero. As a result, EVs receive no reward for maintaining optimal speeds. The results show that without this reward signal, their behaviour becomes less efficient and less cautious. While the average speed of EVs slightly decreases to 7.04 m/s (7%), this comes with notable performance penalties. The average waiting time of EVs increases to 12.68 s (+29.52%) and emergency braking spikes to 3.44 events (+196.55%), indicating instability and more abrupt manoeuvres. Although the average travel time of all vehicles slightly improves (3.07%), the increase in harsh braking and waiting time suggests that this setting leads to inefficient and less safe EV behaviour for this scenario.

7.2.3.3 | Speed Reward EV Ratio Weighted. Moreover, when the weight is adaptively set to $\frac{N_{EV}}{N_{total}} \times w_s^{(CAV)} = 0.6 \times w_s^{(CAV)}$, EVs reach their highest average speed (8.15 m/s) and lowest average waiting time (8.84 s), showing that proportional reward weighting works well when EVs dominate the environment. This best setting can also be achieved through the adaptive formulation in the proposed MAPPO-WEV method. However, the setting EV/CAV ratio weighted is not applicable due to the absence of CAVs in this scenario.

7.2.3.4 | Speed Reward 1/EV Ratio Weighted. With $N_{EV}=6$, this sets $w_s^{(EV)}$ to $\approx 0.167 w_s^{(CAV)}$. The diminished speed emphasis degrades performance: EV speed falls to 6.37 m/s (-15.85%), while EV trip duration (228.37 s, +88.30%), waiting time (40.67 s, +315.42%), time loss (218.92 s, +95.76%), and total EV travel time (1370.23 s, +88.29%) all increase sharply. Emergency braking also spikes (2.42, +108.62%), indicating more abrupt manoeuvres despite the weaker speed objective. In short, when there are no CAVs and many EVs, making the speed weight too small tends to hurt performance.

7.3 | Impact of Headway Reward Weight on Performance

Table 2 illustrates the impact of changing the headway reward weight ($w_h^{(EV)}$) on EVs' performance. The weight is tested in six settings: the baseline ($w_h^{(EV)}$), EV ratio weighted ($\frac{N_{EV}}{N_{total}} \times w_h^{(CAV)}$), CAV/EV ratio weighted ($\frac{N_{CAV}}{N_{EV}} \times w_h^{(CAV)}$), 2EV/CAV ratio weighted ($\frac{2N_{EV}}{N_{CAV}} \times w_h^{(CAV)}$), EV/CAV ratio weighted ($\frac{N_{EV}}{N_{CAV}} \times w_h^{(CAV)}$), and 1/EV ratio weighted ($\frac{1}{N_{EV}} \times w_h^{(CAV)}$).

7.3.1 | Performance Under Scenario 1

7.3.1.1 | Headway Reward EV Ratio Weighted. In this setting, the headway reward for EVs is scaled according to their proportion in the traffic mix ($\frac{N_{EV}}{N_{total}} \times w_h^{(CAV)}$), resulting in a lower weight compared to the baseline. As a result, EVs place less emphasis on maintaining safe headway distances. This leads to a decrease in average speed of EVs by 17.38%, and increases in average travel time of all vehicles (96.80 s, +25.79%), average trip duration of EVs (136.7 s, +36.47%), and average waiting time of EVs (11.02 s, +101.09%). While emergency braking slightly improves (7.69%) and emergency stops remain close to baseline.

7.3.1.2 | Headway Reward EV/CAV Ratio Weighted and 1/EV Ratio Weighted. With $N_{EV}=2$ and $N_{CAV}=4$, $\frac{N_{EV}}{N_{EV}} = \frac{1}{N_{EV}} = 0.5$. Thus, EV/CAV and 1/EV both set $w_h^{(EV)} = 0.5 w_h^{(CAV)}$ and yield identical outcomes: EV speed drops to 4.45 m/s (-25.08%), while travel-time metrics worsen—all-vehicle travel time +42.00%, EV trip duration 165.43 s (+65.15%), waiting 15.67 s (+185.77%), and time loss 155.91 s (+71.98%). Emergency braking improves slightly (-8.65%), but stops increase (+19.64%).

7.3.1.3 | Headway Reward CAV/EV Ratio Weighted. In Scenario 1 when the headway reward is doubled ($\frac{N_{CAV}}{N_{EV}} \times w_h^{(CAV)} = 2 \times w_h^{(CAV)}$), the results show a significant decline in EVs' performance. The average travel time of all vehicles rises sharply by 82.26%, and both the average waiting time (21.43 s) and the average trip duration of EVs (207.42 s) increase substantially compared to the Baseline. This is primarily because giving higher headway weight reward causes EVs to behave overly conservatively, maintaining large gaps from other vehicles and slowing down in order to avoid penalties for short following distances. As a result, EVs become hesitant to merge or manoeuvre, leading to increased delay.

7.3.1.4 | Headway Reward 2×EV/CAV Ratio Weighted. This setting for headway reward achieves the best balance across all metrics. It maintains a reasonable average travel time (76.94 s) and average trip duration (100.15 s), while minimizing abrupt stops and maintaining a moderate average speed (5.94 m/s). This finding aligns with the proposed MAPPO-WEV headway reward weight for EVs based on the Equation (10) that suggests the best performance for this scenario is when the $w_h^{(EV)}$ is equal to $w_h^{(EV)}$.

7.3.1.5 | Average EV Waiting Time Under Different Headway Reward Weights. Figure 4 shows the average EV waiting time across training episodes for six distinct headway weight settings in Scenario 1: baseline in red, CAV/EV ratio weighted in green, EV ratio weighted in purple, EV/CAV ratio weighted and 1/EV ratio weighted in blue. The curve for 2 × EV/CAV ratio weighted coincides with the baseline in Scenario 1; hence only four distinct traces appear. The findings mirror Table 2: the Baseline (overlapping with 2 × EV/CAV) attains the lowest waiting times, the CAV/EV ratio setting yields the highest (overly conservative headway), and the EV ratio setting, 1/EV ratio weighted, and EV/CAV ratio weighted sit in between. This pattern also matches the MAPPO-WEV rule in Equation (10): for Scenario 1 it selects $w_h^{(EV)} = w_h^{(CAV)} \cdot \frac{2N_{EV}}{N_{CAV}} = w_h^{(CAV)}$, which corresponds to the lowest observed EV waiting time curve.

7.3.2 | Performance Under Scenario 2

7.3.2.1 | Headway reward EV/CAV Ratio Weighted. Here $N_{EV} = 4$ and $N_{CAV} = 2$, so $\frac{N_{EV}}{N_{CAV}} = 2$ and $w_h^{(EV)} = 2w_h^{(CAV)}$. This stronger headway emphasis raises EV speed to 5.44 m/s (+56.78%) and markedly improves efficiency relative to Baseline: all-vehicle travel time 90.77 s (−61.15%), EV trip duration 122.61 s (−60.57%), waiting 12.00 s (−77.49%), time loss 103.20 s (−65.75%), and total EV travel time 510.46 s (−58.96%). Safety is somewhat worse (stops 1.18, +9.26%; braking 2.52, +31.25%), indicating more assertive manoeuvres compared to the baseline.

7.3.2.2 | Headway Reward CAV/EV Ratio Weighted. In Scenario 2, which includes 4 EVs, 2 CAVs, and 4 HDVs, using an adaptive weight such as $\frac{N_{CAV}}{N_{EV}} \times w_h^{(CAV)}$ results in significantly improved EV performance. The average trip duration drops from 310.91 s (Baseline) to 144.22 s, and the average time loss decreases from 301.50 to 134.80 s. Furthermore, the average speed of EVs increases by 99.71%. This setting also reduces the waiting time of EVs from 53.31 to 13.73 s. However, a slight rise in emergency braking (2.26) and emergency stops (1.14) indicates that more assertive driving behaviours may introduce mild safety concerns. In this setting, the highest average speed of EVs does not correspond to the lowest average trip duration. In this setting, the relationship between average speed and average trip duration is not straightforward. The speed metric averages per-trip speeds $v_i = L/d_i$ (with fixed L), while the duration metric averages the d_i themselves. For example, with the same route length L , suppose three EVs have baseline trip times [120, 120, 120] s. After a change, two EVs become faster [90, 90] s while one EV is much slower [300] s. The average trip duration increases from 120 s to $(90 + 90 + 300)/3 = 160$ s, yet the average speed increases: from $L/120$ to $(L/90 + L/90 + L/300)/3 \approx 1.02 \times (L/120)$. In short, even though the average duration goes up, the average speed can still go up.

7.3.2.3 | Headway Reward 2×EV/CAV Ratio Weighted. Increasing the headway reward weight of EVs using the setting $\frac{2N_{EV}}{N_{CAV}} \times w_h^{(CAV)}$ improves the average speed of EVs (5.68 m/s) and reduces the average waiting time of EVs (10.10 s). This also leads to the shortest average trip duration (111.61 s) and lowest average time loss of EVs (102.19 s) among all tested weights. Although the safety comes at a risk, as emergency braking increases by 13.54%, the emergency stops is almost the same as the Baseline.

7.3.2.4 | Headway Reward EV Ratio Weighted. In this case, the headway reward weight for EVs is decreased based on their share in the traffic composition ($\frac{N_{EV}}{N_{total}} \times w_h^{(CAV)} = 0.4 \times w_h^{(CAV)}$). Compared to the baseline, this setting leads to substantial improvements across most performance metrics. The average trip duration of EVs drops by 49%, the average time loss of EVs decreases by 50.52%, and the average waiting time of EVs reduces significantly by 68.11%. Additionally, the average travel time of all vehicles falls by 47.65%, indicating improved overall traffic flow. However, these efficiency gains come at the cost of increased emergency stops (+14.81%) and emergency braking (+16.67%).

7.3.2.5 | Headway Reward 1/EV Ratio Weighted. Setting $w_h^{(EV)} = \frac{1}{N_{EV}} w_h^{(CAV)} = 0.25 w_h^{(CAV)}$ gives solid but not best results:

EV speed 5.20 m/s (+49.86%), trip duration 127.42 s (−59.02%), waiting 18.02 s (−66.20%), time loss 118.00 s (−60.86%), and total EV travel time 509.68 s (−59.02%). Safety metrics soften only a little (stops 1.14, +5.56%; braking 2.14, +11.46%). Overall, it trails the $2 \times$ EV/CAV setting on efficiency.

Notably, all adaptive weight settings in Scenario 2 perform better than the Baseline, which supports the idea of using a dynamic reward adjustment based on vehicle ratios. Among them, the best overall performance is achieved at $\frac{2N_{EV}}{N_{CAV}} \times w_h^{(CAV)}$, consistent with Equation (10), which suggests adapting the weight based on vehicle penetration rates in the traffic composition.

7.3.3 | Performance Under Scenario 3

7.3.3.1 | Headway reward EV Ratio Weighted. In Scenario 3, with 6 EVs and 4 HDVs (no CAVs), the results again indicate the importance of adjusting the reward weight contextually. When the reward is set to $\frac{N_{EV}}{N_{total}} \times w_h^{(CAV)} = 0.6 \times w_h^{(CAV)}$, EVs achieve their highest average speed (8.46 m/s), shortest average trip duration (95.71 s), and lowest average time loss (86.26 s). This setting also reduces the average waiting time of EVs by 38.75%, while maintaining a moderate safety level (emergency stops = 1.12).

7.3.3.2 | Headway Reward CAV/EV Ratio Weighted. Decreasing the headway reward to $\frac{N_{CAV}}{N_{EV}} \times w_h^{(CAV)} = 0$, since no CAVs being present, leads to a significant drop in performance. The average travel time of all vehicles increases to 146.52 s, and the total travel time of EVs jumps to 1191.08 s. Additionally, the average time loss of EVs increases sharply to 189.05 s, and the average waiting time of EVs rises to 27.19 s. This setting makes EVs less cautious in terms of keeping a safe headway, harming their mobility and response times.

7.3.3.3 | Headway Reward 1/EV Ratio Weighted. With $N_{EV}=6$, this sets $w_h^{(EV)} \approx 0.167 w_h^{(CAV)}$. It yields modest efficiency gains versus baseline (EV speed 7.85 m/s, +3.70%; trip duration 113.29 s, −6.59%; time loss 103.84 s, −7.14%) but at a safety cost (stops 1.60, +21.21%; braking 2.48, +113.79%). In EV-dominant traffic with no CAVs, too small a headway weight tends to backfire.

These outcomes confirm that neglecting headway distance is not suitable when EVs dominate and must make timely manoeuvres in the absence of automated vehicles. These results demonstrate that the optimal headway reward weight for EVs is achieved by adaptively scaling it based on the traffic composition, as proposed by MAPPO-WEV method.

7.4 | Impact of merging reward weight on performance

The results in Table 3 demonstrate the effect of dynamically adapting the merging reward weight on the performance of EVs ($w_m^{(EV)}$). The merging reward is varied at five settings: baseline ($w_m^{(CAV)}$), half CAV/EV ratio weighted ($\frac{w_m^{(CAV)}}{2} \times \frac{N_{CAV}}{N_{EV}}$),

CAV/EV ratio weighted ($w_m^{(CAV)} \times \frac{N_{CAV}}{N_{EV}}$), half weight ($\frac{1}{2} \times w_m^{(CAV)}$), and EV/CAV ratio weighted ($w_m^{(CAV)} \times \frac{N_{EV}}{N_{CAV}}$).

$w_m^{(EV)} = \left(\frac{w_m^{(CAV)} N_{CAV}}{2 N_{EV}} \right) = w_m^{(CAV)}$, which corresponds to the red curve with the lowest observed EV waiting time.

7.4.1 | Performance Under Scenario 1

7.4.1.1 | Merging Reward CAV/EV Ratio Weighted. In Scenario 1 when the merging reward is doubled $w_m^{(CAV)} \times \frac{N_{CAV}}{N_{EV}}$, the system exhibits a notable drop in efficiency. EVs attempt to over-prioritize minimizing time spent in the merging lane, which leads to suboptimal decisions, such as merging into tighter gaps or decelerating abruptly. This behaviour contributes to a reduction in average speed of EVs (4.49 m/s) and significant increases in average travel time of all vehicles (108.79 s), average waiting time of EVs (17.75 s), and average trip duration of EVs (160.79 s). The higher frequency of emergency stops (1.34) and braking events (2.10) further suggests that this aggressive merging strategy increases the safety risks. The findings suggest that over-emphasizing merging reward is not a good decision when there is a few number of EVs.

7.4.1.2 | Merging Reward EV/CAV Ratio Weighted, Half Weight, and 1/EV Ratio Weighted. In contrast, reducing the merging reward to half its original value ($\frac{1}{2} \times w_m^{(CAV)} = \frac{N_{EV}}{N_{CAV}} \times w_m^{(CAV)} = \frac{1}{N_{EV}} \times w_m^{(CAV)}$) yields more balanced outcomes. EVs exhibit smoother merging behaviour, as indicated by improved metrics including lower emergency stops (0.86), emergency braking (1.72), and improved time loss and waiting time of EVs in comparison to the first setting. Although average speed (5.25 m/s) and travel time (87.12 s) are not as optimal as in the Baseline, the results suggest that a lower merging reward encourages more cooperative and context-aware behaviour, especially when sufficient CAVs are present to assist with spacing and coordination.

7.4.1.3 | Merging Reward Half CAV/EV Ratio Weighted. This setting of the merging reward provides the best trade-off between responsiveness and stability. It achieves the most consistent results across efficiency, safety, and speed, with a reasonable average travel time of all vehicles (76.94 s), moderate number of braking and stop events, and the highest average speed of EVs (5.94 m/s) among all settings. This again shows that the Equation (11) of the proposed MAPPO-WEV method results in selecting the best setting. However, similar to the headway reward weight, the merging reward weight for EVs is also tied to the penetration rate of EVs and CAVs in the traffic flow.

7.4.1.4 | Average EV Waiting Time Under Different Merging Reward Weights. Figure 5 plots the average EV waiting time across training episodes for merging reward weight settings in Scenario 1: baseline shown in red; CAV/EV ratio weighted shown in green; EV/CAV ratio weighted, half weight, and 1/EV ratio weighted shown in blue. The half CAV/EV ratio weighted setting coincides with baseline here, so only three distinct traces appear. The learning trends mirror Table 3: red (baseline) consistently attains the lowest waiting times, blue line sits in the middle, and green line is highest. This matches the MAPPO-WEV rule in Equation (11): for Scenario 1 it selects

7.4.2 | Performance Under Scenario 2

7.4.2.1 | Merging Reward CAV/EV Ratio Weighted and Half Weight. In Scenario 2, which includes 4 EVs, 2 CAVs, and 4 HDVs, we observe more pronounced differences in performance across the tested settings. When the merging reward weight is decrease using ($\frac{1}{2} \times w_m^{(CAV)} = w_m^{(CAV)} \times \frac{N_{CAV}}{N_{EV}}$), EV performance improves significantly over the baseline. The average travel time of all vehicles improves by 50.52%, and average waiting time of EVs drops from 53.31 s to 17.43 s. The average trip duration of EVs is reduced by over 50% (from 310.91 to 151.59 s), while the average speed of EVs increases by 27%. However, this gain in efficiency comes at the cost of increased emergency manoeuvres, with emergency stops rising to 1.60 and braking events reaching 2.68, indicating slightly more abrupt and less stable driving behaviour.

7.4.2.2 | Merging Reward EV/CAV Ratio Weighted. On the other hand, increasing the merging reward weight using $\frac{N_{EV}}{N_{CAV}} \times w_m^{(CAV)}$ significantly worsens performance. The average waiting time of EVs climbs to 75.63 s, and the total travel time of EVs increases to 1638.67 s, the highest across all scenarios. EVs become overly cautious, slowing down more frequently and struggling to merge efficiently, especially in the absence of sufficient CAV support. This is also reflected in higher average time loss of EVs (400.26 s). A slight increase in average EV speed compare to the baseline is observed (+1.44%); however, the average trip duration still rises. This can occur because the speed metric averages per-trip speeds (proportional to $1/d_i$) across EVs/episodes, whereas trip duration averages the d_i themselves, so a few EVs with very long delays can raise mean duration even when most EVs travel marginally faster. This suggests that over-penalizing time spent in the merging lane creates hesitation and bottlenecks.

7.4.2.3 | Merging Reward Half CAV/EV Ratio Weighted and 1/EV Ratio Weighted. Notably, the best overall performance is achieved when the merging reward is scaled using $\frac{w_m^{(CAV)}}{2} \times \frac{N_{CAV}}{N_{EV}}$. This setting yields the lowest average travel time of all vehicles (75.95 s), the shortest trip duration of EVs (101.64 s), and the fastest average speed of EVs (6.82 m/s), while significantly reducing average waiting time (8.58 s), average time loss (92.22 s), and average total travel time (406.59 s) of EVs compared to the baseline. Although emergency manoeuvres increase moderately, the overall performance suggests a well-balanced reward design that promotes efficient and assertive merging without compromising stability.

These findings emphasize that the best performing setting is achieved when the merging reward is adapted to the relative share of CAVs in the environment, as proposed in MAPPO-WEV method. In this case, the weight $\frac{w_m^{(CAV)}}{2} \times \frac{N_{CAV}}{N_{EV}}$ achieved the lowest response times for EVs.

TABLE 4 | Comparison of baseline versus simultaneous adjustment of all reward signals across three scenarios. Percentages on “simultaneous” rows indicate change relative to the corresponding baseline.

Scenario	Setting	Vehicle type	Performance metrics			
			Avg travel time	Avg waiting time	Avg time loss	Avg speed
Scenario 1	Baseline	EV	100.15	5.48	90.63	5.94
	Simultaneous	EV	92.31 (−7.83%)	4.24 (−22.63%)	82.78 (−8.66%)	8.65 (+45.62%)
	Baseline	CAV	103.6	11.41	87.88	7.04
	Simultaneous	CAV	98.88 (−4.56%)	11.32 (−0.79%)	85.18 (−3.07%)	8.06 (+14.49%)
	Baseline	HDV	48.51	1.12	33.30	11.44
	Simultaneous	HDV	38.41 (−20.82%)	0.63 (−43.75%)	23.19 (−30.36%)	14.26 (+24.65%)
Scenario 2	Baseline	EV	310.91	53.31	301.50	3.47
	Simultaneous	EV	81.61 (−73.75%)	7.82 (−85.33%)	72.08 (−76.09%)	8.15 (+134.87%)
	Baseline	CAV	276.46	51.25	200.50	7.12
	Simultaneous	CAV	103.24 (−62.66%)	12.39 (−75.82%)	87.54 (−56.34%)	7.44 (+4.49%)
	Baseline	HDV	79.55	6.71	64.34	11.64
	Simultaneous	HDV	59.48 (−25.23%)	2.45 (−63.49%)	44.26 (−31.21%)	12.81 (+10.05%)
Scenario 3	Baseline	EV	121.28	9.79	111.83	7.57
	Simultaneous	EV	73.12 (−39.71%)	4.83 (−50.66%)	63.67 (−43.07%)	9.87 (+30.38%)
	Baseline	CAV	0	0	0	0
	Simultaneous	CAV	0	0	0	0
	Baseline	HDV	49.03	0.90	33.81	11.70
	Simultaneous	HDV	38.65 (−21.17%)	0.70 (−22.22%)	23.42 (−30.73%)	13.43 (+14.79%)

7.4.3 | Performance Under Scenario 3

7.4.3.1 | The Baseline Merging Reward Weight. In Scenario 3, which contains 6 EVs and 4 HDVs and no CAVs, we observe a different pattern due to the absence of CAV support. Here, the baseline setting provides the best trade-off between efficiency and safety. The average travel time is the lowest (90.54 s), and the average speed of EVs reaches 7.57 m/s, while keeping emergency stops and braking events at manageable levels (1.32 and 1.16, respectively).

7.4.3.2 | Merging Reward CAV/EV Ratio Weighted and Half CAV/EV Ratio Weighted. When the merging reward weight is decrease using $\frac{N_{CAV}}{N_{EV}} \times w_m^{(CAV)} = 0$, performance declines sharply. The average travel time increases to 111.69 s, average time loss of EVs rises to 135.99 s, and emergency braking spikes to 2.58. These results highlight that while the merging reward weight should adapt to the number of CAVs, it should not be reduced to zero, even in their absence, as this leads to significantly degraded performance.

7.4.3.3 | Merging Reward Half Weight. Interestingly, reducing the reward to $\frac{1}{2} \times w_m^{(CAV)}$ improves performance in this CAV-free scenario. It yields lower emergency stops (1.14), the lowest emergency braking (0.82), and smoother merging with a moderate average speed (6.12 m/s). These outcomes show that in the absence of supportive automated vehicles, less emphasis on merging speed allows EVs to behave more cautiously and safely.

7.4.3.4 | Merging Reward 1/EV Ratio Weighted. When the merging weight is set to $\frac{1}{N_{EV}} w_m^{(CAV)}$ (here $\frac{1}{6} \approx 0.17$), performance degrades significantly relative to the baseline: average travel time of all vehicles rises from 90.54 to 257.19 s, average waiting time of EVs from 9.79 to 71.47 s, and average time loss of EVs from 111.83 to 336.54 s, while the mean EV speed drops from 7.57 to 4.70 m/s. In the absence of CAV support, the low merging penalty makes it difficult for EVs to merge, leading to increased delays.

Overall, these findings confirm that the merging reward weight for EVs should not be fixed but instead be dynamically adjusted based on the presence and ratio of CAVs. The most effective settings are those that align with Equation (11) of MAPPO-WEV method, which captures the need for adaptive reward tuning in different traffic compositions.

7.5 | Simultaneous Weight Adjustment of Reward Signals

Table 4 compares the baseline against the simultaneous adjustment of all EV reward weights. In this table, MAPPO-WEV is used to jointly adjust the speed, merging, and headway reward weights for EVs, and the results are compared with the baseline, where EVs and CAVs share the same reward weights. In **Scenario 1**, EVs show notable improvements: trip duration decreases by 7.83%, waiting times by 22.63%, time loss by 8.66%, and speed increases by 45.62%. CAVs and HDVs also improve (e.g., CAV speed +14.49%, HDV waiting time −43.75%). In **Scenario 2**,

the gains are strongest for EVs (trip duration -73.75% , waiting time -85.33% , time loss -76.09% , speed $+134.87\%$), with parallel improvements for CAVs and HDVs (e.g., CAV travel time -62.66% , HDV waiting time -63.49%). In **Scenario 3** (no CAVs), EVs still benefit substantially (trip duration -39.71% , waiting time -50.66% , time loss -43.07% , speed $+30.38\%$), along with HDVs (e.g., time loss -30.73% , speed $+14.79\%$).

When all EV weights are adapted jointly, the greatest improvements can be observed, as the policy reduces waiting times, decreases time-loss travel times, and improves speeds. This yields shorter trips and higher trip speeds across vehicle classes, especially where EV urgency is higher or CAV support is limited (Scenarios 2–3), aligning with MAPPO-WEV's design goal. Importantly, simultaneous tuning with MAPPO-WEV did not degrade the performance of the other vehicle classes. On the contrary, CAVs and HDVs generally improved or held steady across all scenarios.

The apparent deviation in baseline performance metrics for Scenario 2, compared to the other scenarios, arises from its more heterogeneous vehicle composition and the fixed reward weight setting for different vehicle types. In Scenario 2, EVs operate under non-optimized reward weights that are unsuitable for higher EV penetration. This imbalance leads to conflicting behaviours, with CAVs maintaining headway and speed while EVs attempt to merge or overtake, causing severe delays and unstable traffic dynamics. Once all reward weights are simultaneously adapted, coordination between EVs and CAVs improves substantially, reducing EV travel time by 73.8% and increasing average speed by 135% . In contrast, the more homogeneous Scenario 3 (comprising only EVs and HDVs) exhibits better Baseline performance due to the more uniform traffic flow.

Additionally, it should be noted that better HDV performance is due to the imposed minimum speed of 10 m/s , which ensures stable driving and prevents excessive stops under congestion. This lower bound slightly raises their average metrics compared with adaptive CAV and EV agents, which dynamically adjust speeds based on interactions and priorities.

7.6 | Vehicle Density

Figure 6 presents a spatiotemporal heatmap of vehicle density over time and space in the SUMO traffic simulation. It visualizes how vehicles are distributed along the road (in meters) over time (in seconds), and how their density evolves. Higher densities are indicated by darker colours. The red-shaded area represents the merging zone, and the blue-shaded area corresponds to the work zone.

Baseline density: Figure 6a illustrates the baseline setting, which shows more high-density areas (darker regions), especially within and beyond the work zone. The vertical axis reveals that these high-density conditions persist for an extended period (more than 400 s).

Adaptive speed reward weight: In contrast, the adaptive speed reward weight (Figure 6b) results in fewer high-density areas

(a) Baseline weight rewards in Scenario 3

(b) Adaptive speed weight reward using EV Ratio Weighted in Scenario 3

(c) Adaptive headway weight reward using EV Ratio Weighted in Scenario 3

(d) Adaptive Merging weight reward using Baseline merging reward weight in Scenario 3

FIGURE 6 | Comparison of vehicle density for Scenario 3 under three different reward weight settings.

FIGURE 7 | Average vehicle delay based on the scenario.

across all regions, with no significant congestion observed after 100 s.

Adaptive headway reward weight: Figure 6c, corresponds to the adaptive headway reward weight, which shows even fewer high-density areas overall and a faster trip completion by 150 s.

Adaptive merging reward weight: The merging weight (Figure 6d) adaptation produces results similar to the Baseline, and this shows that for Scenario 3, the best merging reward weight is the Baseline merging reward weight, which could be achieved via Equation (11).

7.7 | Delay Versus Penetration Rate

Figure 7 presents the average delay for each setting, grouped by scenario. Green bars represent the delay experienced by EVs and orange bars represent the delay for CAVs. It is important to note that EVs are inserted into the simulation after the CAVs. This leads to longer travel and waiting times for EVs, as they are delayed by vehicles ahead of them, causing them to have longer vehicle delays and travel times. The delay shown in the figure is defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Travel delay} &= \text{Average travel time (with work zone)} \\ &- \text{Baseline travel time (no work zone)} \quad (12) \end{aligned}$$

The bar chart highlights improvements in all scenarios for both EVs and CAVs. These improvements are especially notable in scenarios with higher EV penetration rates, particularly when CAVs are also present in the network. This suggests that the combined presence of EVs and CAVs contributes to more efficient traffic flow under the modified reward strategies.

8 | Conclusion and Future Works

This study addressed the challenge of managing mixed traffic, including EVs, CAVs, and HDVs in work zone environments, where merging behaviours often lead to congestion and increased delays for EVs. This leads to an increase in their response times. We proposed MAPPO-WEV, a reward weight adjustment method integrated into a MAPPO framework. The method dynamically

adjusts the reward weights for speed, headway, and merging behaviours based on the traffic composition. Simulation results across multiple scenarios demonstrated that adapting reward weights based on vehicle demands significantly improves EV performance metrics, including reduced travel time, waiting time, and time loss—without negatively affecting the efficiency of CAVs or overall traffic flow. Specifically, the best-performing settings consistently aligned with our proposed formulations for adaptive reward weighting (Equations 9–11). These settings allowed EVs to manoeuvre more efficiently, even in congested conditions, while maintaining acceptable safety levels. Among the different reward signals, speed reward adjustments had the strongest influence on EV efficiency, followed closely by headway reward, while merging reward adjustments showed smaller marginal gains. Our density and delay analyses further confirmed that adaptive reward weighting leads to quicker traffic dissipation and reduced network-wide congestion, particularly in high EV penetration scenarios with CAV support using their communication capabilities. In conclusion, the MAPPO-WEV framework provides an effective and scalable approach to adaptive reward tuning in mixed autonomy traffic. It offers a path toward intelligent traffic management that prioritizes EV mobility while balancing overall system performance. Future work may explore how we can use RL to learn reward weights dynamically based on the total performance of the traffic network. Additionally, RL could be used to align the objectives of different users (EVs, CAVs, HDVs, and road workers) with the global system objective, such as efficiency.

Author Contributions

Fatemeh Bandarian: conceptualization, formal analysis, investigation, methodology, software, visualization, writing—original draft, writing—review and editing. **Saeedeh Ghanadbashi:** formal analysis, writing—review and editing. **Abdollah Malekjafarian:** funding acquisition, project administration, supervision. **Fatemeh Golpayegani:** formal analysis, funding acquisition, methodology, project administration, supervision, writing—review and editing.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

Data sharing is not applicable to this article as no datasets were generated or analysed during the current study. The results are based on assumed traffic scenarios and simulation-based experiments developed by the authors.

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